

CLASSROOM ORGANIZATION AND MANAGEMENT FOR EFFECTIVE IMPLEMENTATION OF INNOVATIVE CLASSROOM PRACTICES FOR SUSTAINABLE EDUCATIONAL DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA

Dr. Afolabi, F.O

*Department of Educational Administration and Planning
Adeyemi College of Education, Ondo, Ondo State, Nigeria*

Email: afolab52@yahoo.com

and

Afolabi, O.A

*Department of Sociology
University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria*

Email: sheunhayour@yahoo.com

Abstract

The goal of every teacher in the classroom is to impact knowledge and mould the ideas, habits and attitudes of the students with a view to bringing forth learners who are mentally alert, physically strong, culturally sound, economically efficient and emotionable stable. To achieve this laudable goal in the classroom, the teacher adopts various innovative classroom practices. However, effective implementation of such innovative classroom practices depends greatly on effective classroom organisation and management. This study is therefore set out to ascertain the extent to which classroom organizational issues such as physical setting of the classroom in terms of space, illumination, ventilation and aesthetics have created conducive classroom climate that pave way to mutual interaction among the students in the classroom. Also to determine how classroom management in terms of classroom communication, the keeping and maintenance of class records, class discipline and teacher's use of power and authority to enforce students' compliance with class rules and regulations, are being directed towards creating conducive classroom environment for effective implementation of innovative classroom practices for sustainable educational development in Nigeria. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that all education stakeholders, notably parents, guardians, firms, government and others must support the schools financially and procure all resources for effective teaching and learning in the classroom.

KEYWORDS: *Classroom Organization; Classroom Management; Implementation Innovative Classroom Practices; Sustainable Educational Development.*

Introduction

It is a truism that the progress of a nation is being determined primarily in the classroom, where the minds, habits, attitudes and general physique of people

who are to change and preside over the destiny of the nation are being moulded; and where various innovative classroom practices for sustainable educational development are being implemented. In Nigeria, the classroom as an integral part and a microcosm of the school system plays significant role in the implementation of various educational policies at all levels of education, geared towards sustainable development of all facets of the nation. As succinctly remarked by Ogunu (2000), "a classroom is an institutionalized setting for teaching; and a place where a teacher and twenty or more students meet regularly for a designated period of time over an interval of four to nine months." In recent times in Nigeria, many innovative classroom practices have been introduced. These include the adoption of individualised instruction, which is directed towards assisting a student to learn a specified amount of work at his own pace, within stipulated period of time. Individualised instruction could be in form of Computer Assisted Instruction (CAI), Learner Controlled Instruction (LCI), Personalised System of Instruction (PSI), Programme Instruction (PI) and so on. Other innovative classroom practices include the use of Computer Based Test (CBT) for students' evaluation; the use of computers in keeping, storing and retrieving class records and the use of sophisticated electronic gadgets to attract, sustain students' attention and stimulate their curiosity in learning. Ironically, if the classroom is not properly organized and effectively managed, then effective implementation of these innovative classroom practices for sustainable educational development in Nigeria would become an onerous and herculean task to be accomplished.

The primary focus of a well committed teacher in the classroom is to impart knowledge and inculcate desirable habits and attitudes into the students. To release this lofty goal, the teacher embarks on various activities in the classroom such as giving explanations and illustrations on concepts being taught, timely utilization of instructional materials, asking recapitulatory questions, creating room for the students' inquisitiveness, motivating students for learning, organising the classroom to ensure orderliness, managing the classroom to ensure conducive classroom environment and so on. Of all these activities, none is as centrally important as the one relating to the proper organization and effective management of the classroom. Of all the critical problems facing teachers in the classrooms in recent times in Nigeria, none as agonizing, virulent and persistent as the problem of effective organization and management of the

classroom. According to Mishra (2007), “one of the most difficult tasks that a teacher faces is classroom management. The number of students that each teacher is responsible for is increasing. The funds for support staff to help in the classroom are decreasing. This combination means that educators need to learn and implement classroom management skills so that the students can learn.”

The problem of effective organization and management of the classroom in Nigeria educational system has been so critical that it keeps on re-echoing at various capacity-building seminars and workshops organized for teachers and at the periodic meetings of All Nigerian Conference of Principals of Secondary Schools and Conference of Primary School Head-teachers of Nigeria at national and local levels. The classroom is aptly described by Afolabi, Loto, Akinniranye and Fasakin (2018), as “a mini-learning environment in the school system where the teacher moulds the ideas, notions, tenets, habits and attitude of the students with a view to producing well balanced personalities who would be useful to themselves and the society at large.” Therefore, for any meaningful activity to proceed effectively in the classroom, the teacher must properly organize the classroom and promptly identify and judiciously control all disruptive behaviours of the students in the classroom, which militate against the normal class routines and practices, so as to create a conducive classroom management for effective implementation of innovative classroom practices for sustainable educational development in Nigeria. As remarked by Cowley (2007), “the key purpose of good classroom management is to create a calm, orderly environment in which proper learning can take place.”

As effective teaching and learning in the classroom can be greatly impaired by inadequate classroom organization, improper sitting arrangement of the students and various disruptive activities of the students. it therefore behoves on the teacher to ensure that all materials and equipment needed for a lesson are readily available and put in their proper places prior to the commencement of the lesson. Also, high premium must be given to the organizational issues in the classroom, such as the physical setting of the classroom in terms of space, illumination, ventilation and aesthetics and creating conducive classroom climate which paves way to mutual interaction among the students. Attention must also be focused on the organization of the instructional materials, equipment and classroom furniture to pave way for working space and mobility in the classroom. Prominent attention must be given to effective management of

classroom with special focus on classroom communication, student motivation for learning, the keeping and maintenance of class records, control of students' disruptive behaviours and teacher's use of power and authority to enforce students' compliance with class rules and regulations: As a way of effectively implementing the various innovative classroom practices for sustainable educational development in Nigeria, the teacher must strive hard to create a conducive classroom environment that will pave way to effective teaching and learning. It is imperative for the teacher to place high premium on proper classroom organization, class arrangement, effective control of students' disruptive behaviours in the classroom and judicious adoption and utilization of principles of classroom management. An attempt is made in this paper to shed more light into the following issues:

1. Who is a professional classroom teacher?
2. What is classroom organisation?
3. What is classroom management?
4. How can the classroom be properly organised for effective teaching and learning?
5. What are the measures for curbing students' disruptive behaviours in the classroom?
6. What model of classroom organisation and management can be set up towards effective implementation of innovative classroom practices for sustainable educational development in Nigeria?

These critical issues are aptly discussed as follows:

Who is a professional class teacher?

A professional teacher occupies a unique position in the educational institution. He is a class manager in his own right and exercises a pervasive influence on the classroom. Mishra (2008), described as professional class teacher as "a living model for the young learners who are under his control and he is to nurture them to make them grow and develop fully so as to make them useful persons for the society and nation. In behaviour and conduct, such professional teacher must possess certain ethics. Then only he should be licensed to work with the pure human nursery." Also, Koleoso (2000), described a professional classroom teacher as a person who has the registrable professional qualification which enables him to be appointed to teach in any recognized

educational institution in Nigeria and who is physically fit of sound mind and mentally alert.

Based on these definitions a professional classroom teacher can be described simply as a designated school official who by virtue of his training and leadership position in the classroom initiates, organizes, directs, controls, motivates, coordinates classroom activities and implements various innovative classroom practices towards ensuring quality instruction. Such professional classroom teachers are always involved in class decision making, motivating students to learn, initiating ideas for effective teaching and learning, analyzing students' problems and finding solution to them and always caring for the students' welfare.

Conceptual Clarification of Terms

Classroom Organisation

The term "Classroom organisation" is simply defined by Afolabi, et al (2018), as "a coordinated set of activities intended to bring about the accomplishment of planned objectives." It is quite obvious from this definition that classroom organisation entails a judicious identification, acquisition and coordination of human resources (the classroom personnel), physical resources (the physical setting of the classroom in terms of classroom doors, windows, floor, ceiling, space, and classroom aesthetics), material resources (instructional materials and classroom furniture), and fiscal resources (funds) earmarked for effective teaching and learning in the classroom.

Classroom Management

The term 'classroom management' has been variously interpreted by different authorities on the subject. Adeboyeje and Afolabi (1992), defined classroom management as a process concerned with identifying, understanding, maintaining, stimulating, controlling and unifying human and material resources in the classroom for maximum success in the teaching-learning situation. Ajayi (2007), defined classroom management simply as "all activities put in place by the teacher and the school head to ensure effective teaching-learning process in the classroom" it is quite obvious in these definitions of the classroom management that the class teacher in his capacity of class manager carries out various management activities in the classroom aimed at achieving the goals of the classroom. Such activities include creating conducive classroom climate that

is, the social climate in the classroom in terms of the way the students interact among themselves as well as interactions with the teacher; having an in-depth knowledge of the students with regards to their background, ability, desires, interest, differences and limitations; judicious use of appropriate instructional methods; improvisation and utilization of instructional materials; motivating students for learning, controlling students' disruptive behaviours; continuous assessment of the students and so on.

Classroom Organisation for effective teaching and learning

Towards ensuring implementation of innovative classroom practices for sustainable educational development in Nigeria, it is highly imperative for the classroom teacher to properly organize his classroom for effective teaching and learning by taking into consideration the following issues:

1. The class teacher must clearly identify all the human, physical and material resources required for effective teaching and learning in the classroom.
2. He must judiciously ascertain the availability and adequacy of the classroom resources by taking critical examination of issues such as the numbers of students in the classroom; level of stakeholders' support for classroom activities; the physical setting of the classroom with special focus on space, ventilation, illumination, insulation from heat and aesthetic values and adequacy of instructional materials and furniture items in the classroom.
3. The class teacher must endeavour to improvise non-available instructional materials as a way of making the teaching-learning a pleasurable activity for the students.
4. As poorly organized instructional materials can pave way to distractions and disorderliness in the classroom, the teacher must judiciously organize the instructional materials in such a way that every student in the classroom has equal opportunity of either seeing the material or using it.
5. To ensure proper organisation of the classroom and prevent any form of students' disorderliness, the class teacher must accord high premium to effective utilization of the instructional materials. The teacher must decide whether to use the instructional materials to introduce the lesson to the students; to develop the lesson; to create rooms for the students'

- inquisitiveness, to summarise the lesson or as a take home assignment for the students.
6. In case of portable magnetic board, such board must be located in front of the class and must be clearly visible from all points in the classroom.
 7. The students' chairs and desks, lockers or tables should be orderly arranged in rows with adequate space provided, so as to ensure that the sitting arrangement of students paves way for harmony.
 8. The seat of the class teacher must be in front of the class, where he could see every student in the class.
 9. It is deemed pertinent that the class monitor should sit nearest to the main entrance to the classroom, so as to facilitate his movement in and out of his seat from time to time, without causing any distraction in the classroom.
 10. The available space provided between the rows in the classroom should be adequate enough to give room for free movement of the students from time to time without disturbing other students or distracting their attention. Also, the quiet corner earmarked for reading in the classroom should be spacious and well ventilated.

Curbing students' disruptive behaviours in the classroom

The students in a typical Nigerian classroom come from various socio-economic and cultural backgrounds and are susceptible to the same learning situation within the confines of the classroom environment. In such unnatural condition, there is always tendency for the students to exhibit all forms of disruptive behaviours in the classroom. As succinctly remarked by Adeboyeje and Afolabi (1992), in the classroom, students are often found exhibiting all forms of disruptive behaviours such as noise making, restlessness in class, shouting at others, whispering when quiet work is going on and flagrant disobedience of class rules and regulations. Thus, to ensure effective implementation of various innovative classroom practices for sustainable educational development in Nigeria, the class teacher must manage the classroom effectively with special focus on the identification and control of students' disruptive activities in the classroom.

Having identified the various disruptive behaviours of the students which tend to hinder normal routines, activities, programmes and practices in the

classroom, the class teacher must adopt feasible measures for curbing these students' disruptive behaviours. Such measures are highlighted as follows:

1. The class teacher must acquaint the students with class rules, regulations, traditions, routines and practices. The class rules and regulations must be enforced.
2. All stringent class rules and regulations must be jettisoned. While commensurate punishment should be administered to erring or mischievous students to serve as deterrent. The class teacher must not be an extremist disciplinarian.
3. The class teacher should serve as a good model for the students and uphold ethics of teaching profession.
4. The teaching-learning process should be made a pleasurable activity through the use of appropriate and relevant instructional materials aimed at stimulating students' curiosity in the lesson and arouse and sustain their interest and attention in the lesson. The teacher must endeavour to use student-centred instructional methods that pave way for students' inquisitiveness and their active participation in class discussion.
5. The teacher must exercise his authority in the classroom. While dictatorial tendencies should be jettisoned.
6. The students should be properly educated on the evil effects of cultism, bribery and corruption and examination malpractice and the need to refrain from them.
7. The class teacher must ensure that the classroom is spacious, well ventilated, sufficiently illuminated, protected from heat and aesthetically pleasing to attract the students to the classroom.
8. The class teacher should be sensitive to the healthy living of the students. While emotional problems of the students must be promptly identified and provide feasible solutions to them.
9. The students should be given adequate attention at home. While parents and guardians should make adequate provision for the school materials of their children and wards.
10. Periodically, the class teacher should furnish the parents and guardians with the academic progress report and general conduct of their children and wards.

A Model of Classroom Organisation and Management for effective implementation of innovative classroom practices for sustainable educational development

A model depicting clearly classroom management for effective implementation of innovative classroom practices for sustainable educational development is indicated in figure 1. The following procedural phases are required for effective classroom organization and management for implementing various innovative classroom practices for sustainable educational development.

1. **Resource identification:** The first indispensable phase in classroom organisation and management for effective implementation of innovative classroom practices for sustainable educational development is a clear identification of resources required for effective teaching and learning in the classroom. These resources can be categorised into four, namely human resources, physical resources, material resources and fiscal resources.
2. **Ascertaining the availability and adequacy of the classroom resources:** The class teacher must determine the extent to which the various classroom resources are available and adequate for effective teaching and learning by examining issues such as number of students in the classroom; level of stakeholders' support for classroom activities; classroom natural conditions in terms of space, ventilation, protection from heat, illumination and aesthetic values and adequacy of instructional materials and classroom furniture.
3. **Improvisation of non-available classroom materials:** The class teacher must strive hard to improvise non-available, but highly essential classroom resources.
4. **Organising and utilising instructional materials for effective teaching and learning:** All the available instructional materials in the classroom must be judiciously organized and timely used to prevent any form of disorderliness in classroom.
5. **Identification and control of students disruptive behaviours in the classroom:** The class teacher must vigilantly identify all forms of students' disruptive behaviours which tend to hinder normal classroom routines, activities, programmes and practices. He must adopt feasible measures for curbing such disruptive behaviours of the students in order

to ensure a conducive classroom environment for effective teaching and learning, which paves way for effective implementation of innovative classroom practices for sustainable educational development

Figure 1: A model of Classroom organisation and management for effective implementation of innovative classroom practices for sustainable educational development. (Designed by the Authors)

Conclusion

A conducive classroom climate is of paramount importance for effective implementation of innovative classroom practices for sustainable educational development. A classroom which has an enervating, excruciating and tense atmosphere does not pave way for effective teaching and learning and implementation of innovative classroom practices. Also, in a classroom where the teacher has no obsolete control of students' activities and does not provide appropriate direction and good leadership to ensure that the classroom environment is conducive enough for effective implementation of innovative classroom practices for sustainable educational development, particularly in Nigeria, thus the students would undoubtedly exhibit all forms of obnoxious disruptive behaviours in the classroom for effective teaching and learning to take place in the classroom through judicious implementation of innovative classroom practices, the class teacher must place high premium on effective classroom organisation and management and adoption of appropriate measures for controlling students' disruptive behaviours in the classroom.

Recommendations

The following recommendations and submissions are made for improvements.

In view of paucity of funds in schools, to procure the required resources for effective implementation of innovative classroom practices for sustainable educational development, all education stakeholders, notably parents, guardians, firms, government and so on must support the schools financially and procure all resources for effective teaching and learning in the classroom.

As the cost of education materials is becoming astronomical daily in Nigeria. It becomes imperative for all stakeholders of education to provide Nigerian schools with modern instructional resources. Many teachers in Nigerian schools today shun the improvisation of instructional materials due to astronomical cost of these materials.

The teacher should judiciously use motivational techniques to stimulate and enliven students' interest and curiosity in learning, encourage efforts and prevent boredom in the learning tasks which he presents to the students.

The class size in terms of the number of students should not be too large for the teacher to manage, so that he could effectively implement various innovative classroom practices for sustainable educational development. Also,

the classroom should be spacious, properly illuminated, well protected from heat and well ventilated.

All class rules and regulations should be clearly formulated and communicated timely to all the students for compliance. The government should place an embargo on the importation of sensational films and movies which tend to corrupt the students. Also, irrational magazines and posters which find their ways to the classroom should be prohibited in the society. Control of students' disruptive behaviours should be a joint responsibility of the class teachers, school administrators, parents and guardians.

Since an awareness and clear understanding of professional ethics contributes significantly to the effective performance of statutory duties of Nigerian teachers, then workshops, seminars, conferences and other capacity-building programmes should be organized regularly for the teachers to further sensitize them on how to effectively organize and manage the classroom for effective implementation of innovative classroom practices for sustainable educational development in Nigeria.

References

- Adeboyeje, R. A and Afolabi, F. O (1992), *Classroom Management*. Ondo: Ife-Oluwa Enterprises Nigeria Limited.
- Afolabi, F. O, Loto. A. B, Akinniranye, O. I and Fasakin, M. O (2018), *A Practical Approach to Classroom Management and School Organisation*. Ondo: Pat-Ade Prints Nig. Ltd.
- Ajayi, I. A (2007), *Issues in School Management*. Ikeja, Lagos: Bola bay Publications.
- Cowley, M. (2007), *Guerilla Guide to Teaching. 2nd Edition*. London: Continuum International Publishing Group.
- Koleoso, Abayomi (2000), *Introduction to Teaching Profession*. Ondo; Alex Publications.
- Mishra, R. C. (2007) *Classroom Management*. New Delhi: A.P.N Publishing Corporation.
- Ogunu, M. (2000), *Introduction to Educational Management*. Benin City; Mabogun Publishers.